

Studies on Stabilities of Cu(II) and Ni(II) Complexes with 2-amino-4-(*p*-methoxy phenyl ethyl)-thiazole

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Complex formation of Cu(II) and Ni(II) ions with 2-amino-4-(*p*-methoxy phenyl ethyl)-thiazole has been studied in 70% (v/v) dioxan by Irving and Rossotti's pH-titration method at different temperatures (25-40°). The metals form 1:1 and 1:2 complexes. Stability constants, log k_1 and log k_2 at 25° are 2.67 and 2.54 for Cu(II) complexes and 2.49 and 2.52 for Ni(II) complex species. The proton ligand stability constants, pK_D' in the mixed solvent is 4.55 at 25°. The overall changes in thermodynamic functions ΔG , ΔH and ΔS during protonation of ligand as well as during complex formation of metals have been evaluated.

A few complexes of thiazoles have been studied¹ in the solid state. Banerjee and Basak² have reported complex formation of few transitional metals by 2-amino-thiazole in aqueous solutions. Relatively little works have been done on the co-ordination behaviour of 4-substituted thiazoles in mixed aqueous medium. Thiazole is a poor base and a poor complexing agent. Due to the presence of NH₂ group at position-2 and *p*-methoxy phenyl ethyl at position-4, the ring nitrogen atom is expected to show more basic character than the unsubstituted thiazole. It was thus found to be of interest to study complex formation of this 4-substituted 2-amino thiazole towards Cu(II) and Ni(II) ions.

The ligand as well as the complexes are insoluble in water. A 70% (v/v) dioxan-water medium was found convenient for this study. Irving and Rossotti's technique³ together with Van Uitert's⁴ empirical corrections of pH meter readings can be used for the evaluation of stoichiometric stability constants.

Experimental

Chemicals and apparatus :

The thiazole was procured from Dash and his co-workers⁵. All other chemicals used were either of B.D.H. 'Analar' quality or of S. Mercks 'G.R.' grade. Dioxan was purified by double distillation over freshly prepared ferrous hydroxide and then over metallic sodium. All solutions were prepared in 70% (v/v) dioxan-water medium. Pure nitrogen gas passed in 70% dioxan - conductivity water mixture was used to expel air from the solutions. The pH meter was standardized with different buffers at pH 4 and pH 9.1.

pH titrations were performed with the following three sets of solutions for each metal-ligand system at

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three different temperatures viz. 25, 32 and 40° :

- (i) HNO₃ + KNO₃set I
- (ii) HNO₃ + KNO₃ + ligand base...set II
- (iii) HNO₃ + KNO₃ + ligand base + metal nitrate...set III

The total volume being 30 ml in each set. Constant ionic strength of 0.1 was maintained by adding requisite amount of KNO₃ solution. The final concentration of HNO₃, ligand base and metal nitrate were 2.5 mM, 4.43 mM and 0.8 mM respectively. The alkali used was 0.1 M.

The pH meter used was one of Naina Electronics (Digital) make.

The contents of the titration vessel were thermostated and purged with nitrogen for about 20-25 minutes. Titration was carried out by adding a small volume of 0.1 M NaOH each time and noting the pH after the attainment of equilibrium.

Calibration of glass electrode :

To make pH meter readings meaningful in aqueous-dioxan medium, the following Van Uitert⁴ empirical corrections were applied. The stoichiometric hydrogen ion concentration, [H⁺], is related to the meter reading, B, in aqueous-dioxan medium by the relation :

$$-\log [H^+] = B + \log U_H^0 - \log \frac{1}{\gamma^{\pm}}$$

The correction factor $\log U_H^0$ was found to be 0.82 for the present solvent composition at 25°. The mean activity coefficient, γ^{\pm} , of the monovalent electrolyte at

0.1 ionic strength and the present solvent composition have been interpolated from the data of Harned and Owen⁵ on hydrochloric acid.

Calculations

From the displacement of titration curves at any pH of set II and set III from set I average number of proton associated with ligand, \bar{n}_A and average number of ligand linked to metal ion, \bar{n} , could be calculated by means of Irving and Rossotti's formulations⁶. The values at 25° are shown in table 1.

Results

TABLE 1—VALUES OF \bar{n}_A , \bar{n} , pL for Cu(II) and Ni(II)-ligand systems, temp. = 25°, $\mu=0.1$ KNO₃

pH *	\bar{n}_A	\bar{n} for		pL for	
		Cu ²⁺	Ni ²⁺	Cu ²⁺	Ni ²⁺
3.75	0.74	0.41	0.27	3.08	3.07
3.95	0.63	0.79	0.63	2.97	2.95
4.35	0.51	1.19	0.99	2.76	2.74
4.75	0.36	1.67	1.30	2.65	2.62
5.25	0.23	1.98	1.76	2.60	2.57
5.75	0.16	2.15	1.85	2.58	2.55

* meter reading, B

From the table it is clear that even in the presence of excess of ligand \bar{n}_A did not exceed 1. The stability constant of the protonated ligand was, thus, obtained⁶ from the usual plot of pH vs $\log \frac{\bar{n}_A}{1-\bar{n}_A}$. The value of pH at logarithm term = 0, was corrected for mixed solvent composition and the value of pK_D was then noted at all the experimental temperatures. Similarly, for the determination of successive stability constants of the complexes, the values of free ligand concentration, [L], were calculated³ by taking stoichiometric hydrogen ion concentration obtained after proper correction being made on meter readings for mixed solvent used, and corrected values of pK_D at different temperatures.

The stepwise stability constants of the complexes were determined from graphical extrapolation method suggested by Poulsen, Bjerrum and Poulsen⁷. Thus, a series of functions, $f_1, f_2 \dots$ can be constructed from the relation :

$$\bar{n} = \frac{\beta_1 [L] + 2\beta_2 [L]^2 + \dots}{1 + \beta_1 [L] + \beta_2 [L]^2 + \dots} \quad \dots (1)$$

$$\text{Then, } f_1 = \frac{\bar{n}}{[L]} = \frac{\beta_1 + 2\beta_2 [L] + \dots}{1 + \beta_1 [L] + \beta_2 [L]^2 + \dots} \quad \dots (2)$$

$$\text{and } f_2 = \frac{f_1 - \beta_1}{[L]} = \frac{2\beta_2 - \beta_1^2 - \beta_1 \beta_2 [L] + \dots}{1 + \beta_1 [L] + \beta_2 [L]^2 + \dots} \quad \dots (3)$$

From extrapolation of straight line graphs obtained by plotting f_1 vs [L], β_1 could be obtained at [L]=0. Similarly, from equation (3), plots of f_2 vs. [L] would give $2\beta_2 - \beta_1^2$ at [L]=0. From these, β_2 could be calculated. In the present investigations, the latter gave straight lines parallel to concentration axis. These show that only two complexes are present in each of the systems.

The limits of error were checked by calculating standard deviation, σ , on \bar{n} and \bar{n}_A by usual procedure⁸. This was found to be low (± 0.02). It was further checked by other standard methods^{9,10}. The data on $\log \beta_n$ were found to be within variation of ± 0.02 of the experimental values.

Fig 1 shows titration curves at 32°. Fig 2 shows formation curves at 32° and 40°. Fig 3 shows plots of f_1 and f_2 vs [L]. To save space, curves at 25° are not shown, but the data are presented in table 1. Likewise, the data at 32° and 40° are not tabulated and plots of f_1 and f_2 are shown only at one representative temperature, viz. 25°.

Fig. 1. pH-titration curves at 32°

- : acid
- ▲— : acid + ligand
- : acid + ligand + Ni(ii) ions
- △— : acid + ligand + Cu(II) ions

Fig. 2. Formation curves at 32° and 40°.

--- 32°
— 40°

Fig. 3. Graphical evaluation of successive stability constants of metal complexes.
(25°, $\mu = 0.1 M$)

The values of \bar{n}_A indicate that though the ligand has two basic nitrogen atoms only one proton is taken up by it, like phenanthroline and imidazole^{11,12}. This was also observed by Banerjee and Basak² in their works with unsubstituted 2-amino-thiazole.

Thermodynamic parameters :

For the proton-ligand association reaction as well as for the metal-ligand complex formation reactions, the thermodynamic parameters, ΔG , ΔH and ΔS were calculated by using standard equations¹³. The values are shown in Table 2.

TABLE 2—VALUES OF LOG β_x , ΔG_x , ΔH_x and ΔS_x for proton-ligand and metal-ligand complexes*.

temp. = 25°, $\mu = 0.1 KNO_3$

	Proton-ligand system	Metal-ligand system	
		Cu ²⁺	Ni ²⁺
log β_1^2	4.55	2.67	2.49
log β_2^2	—	5.21	5.01
— ΔG_1 , k cal/mole	6.17	3.58	3.31
— ΔG_2 , k cal/mole	—	7.00	6.76
— ΔH_1 , k cal/mole	5.07	5.80	6.50
— ΔH_2 , k cal/mole	—	10.00	9.70
— ΔS_1 , cal/degree	5.00	7.40	10.40
— ΔS_2 , cal/degree	—	10.00	10.00

* The values of ΔG_x , ΔH_x and ΔS_x reported here based on log β_x values at different temperatures (25-40°) with in variation of ± 0.02 of the experimental values.

The values of log β_2 and the three thermodynamic parameters of ML_2^{2+} complex species of Cu²⁺ and Ni²⁺ are higher than the corresponding values of proton-ligand complex species, LH^+ . These indicate higher stabilities of metal-ligand complexes than the protonated ligand. The stability constant of metal complexes follow the Irving-William's sequence. The negative values of ΔS indicate that the complex ions are solvated and the ligand is mono functional towards both H⁺ and metal ions. Because, if the ligand acted as bifunctional in the complex species ML_2^{2+} both primary and tertiary nitrogen atoms would have been used up in complex formation and this would cause a positive entropy rise¹⁴.

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